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ORIGINAL RESEARCH

EFFECT OF KAPALBHATI ON BODY FAT PERCENTAGE AND WATER CONTENT AMONG UNIVERSITY YOGINIS

SATPAL Yadav, M.Phil¹, Dr. A. S. SAJWAN, Ph.D.² Dr. BALJINDER Singh Bal³¹Department Physical Education, Lovely Professional University, Phagwara, Punjab (INDIA)²Lakshmbai National University of Physical Education, Gwalior, Madhya Pradesh (INDIA)³Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar Punjab, INDIA**Abstract:**

The present study aimed at assessing the effect of Kapalbhathi on body fat percentage and water content among University Yoginis. The subjects for the study were selected on the basis of random group design. Thirty (N=30) female students were selected as subject for the present study from Lakshmbai National University of Physical Education (Deemed University), Gwalior (Madhya Pradesh) INDIA. The entire subject ranged between the chronological age of 17 to 22 years. Experiment treatment was then assigned to group “A” while group “B” acts as control. Body composition analyzer was used to measure the Body Fat Percentage and Body Water content. The subjects underwent training for 12-week with the Kapalbhathi. The difference in the mean of each group for selected variables was tested for the significance of difference by paired ‘t’ test. The level of significance was set at 0.05. The result has shown the significant effect in body fat percentage since cal. $t (=3.742) > \text{tab } t. 05(14) (=2.145)$. The treatment of twelve week Kapalbhathi training programme also shown significant improvement in case of body water content, since cal. $t (=6.722) > \text{tab } t.05 (14) (2.145)$.

Keywords: Kapalbhathi, Body Fat, Body Water Content.**INTRODUCTION**

In recent years there has been considerable interest in scientific research on yoga in India and in the west. Today yoga being a subject of varied interest, has gained worlds wide popularity. [1] Yoga has both preventive and therapeutic benefits. The process of Kapalbhathi is related to the breathing process; however it is not a type of pranayam. But, certain sadhakas think in this manner and study Kapalbhathi under the impression that they are studying a type of pranayam. However, process of cleaning the wind pipe is one of the shuddhikriya. [2] The nature of every yogic practice is Psycho Physiological and if this conceptual background is not clearly understood, the whole outlook on yogic practices will be disturbed. The relation of yogic practice in terms of anatomy and physiology would remove many misconceptions about them. [3] The word Kapalbhathi is made up of two words, kapal meaning skull (skull includes all the organs under the skull too) and bhathi means shining, illuminating. Body composition refers to the relative amounts of the different compounds in the body. Typically, researchers have focused on the proportion of the body mass that is water, protein, mineral and fat. The assessment of body composition is generally performed in order to determine and monitor one’s health and fitness status, and to aid in planning training programs for athletes. [4] In this article, the effect of Kapalbhathi on Body Fat Percentage and Body Water Content will be presented and discussed.

METHODS

SUBJECTS

The subjects for the present were selected on the basis of random group design. Thirty (N=30) male students were selected as subject for the present study from Lakshmbai National University of Physical Education (Deemed University) Gwalior, INDIA. All subjects ranged between the chronological age of 17-22 years. The selected subjects were further divided into two groups. Experimental treatment was then assigned to group “A” and group “B” acts as control. The subjects were subjected to a twelve week Kapalbhathi training programme.

SELECTION OF VARIABLES

To find out the effect of Kapalbhathi among students of Lakshmbai National Institute of Physical Education, the following variables were selected for the study.

1. Body Fat Percentage
2. Body Water Content

TEST ADMINISTRATION

BODY FAT PERCENTAGE

Body Fat Percentage was measure by body composition analyzer. The subject was made to step on the scale and weight was taken. It gives the most accurate reading first time in the morning, on an empty stomach. Wear no shoes and minimal clothing, if any at all. Write down the weight. The body-fat analyzer has two galvanized handles to hold, a painless current of electricity is sent to upper body to measure the amount of subcutaneous fluid underneath skin. This is the body fat. To find out the body-fat percentage, input all of the information requested on the digital screen of the analyzer. Press the galvanized handles firmly, hit the "Start" button, extend your arms out straight and wait 7 seconds. Now write down your body-fat percentage. Use a calculator to multiply your weight by your body-fat percentage. For example, if you weigh 180 lbs. and you have 10 percent body fat, your body-fat mass is 18 lbs.

BODY WATER CONTENT

Body Water Content was measure by body composition analyzer, flowing afterglow mass spectrometry FA-MS measurement of water abundance in breath samples from individuals. A known dose of deuterated water (Heavy water, D₂O) is ingested and allowed to equilibrate within the body water. The FA-MS instrument then measures the deuterium-to-hydrogen (D: H) ratio in the exhaled breath water vapour. The total body water is then accurately measured from the increase in breath deuterium content in relation to the volume of D₂O ingested.

SAMPLE PRINTOUT OF BODY COMPOSITION VARIABLES

		10/SEP/2002 16:58	
		BODY TYPE	STANDARD
		GENDER	MALE
		AGE	22
		HEIGHT	176 cm
		WEIGHT	80.3kg
		BMI	25.9
BMR: Basal Metabolic Rate	→	BMR	8138 kJ
			1945 kcal
		FAT%	18.7%
		FAT MASS	15.0kg
		FFM	65.3kg
		TBW	47.8kg
TBW: Total Body Water	→	DESIRABLE RANGE	
		FAT%	8-20%
		FAT MASS	5.7-16.3kg
			FAT MASS:
			Total weight of fat in the body
			←←
			FFM: Fat Free Mass, ie muscle, bone, tissue, water

TWELVE WEEK OF KAPALBHATHI TRAINING PROGRAMME

In the present study the following five stages were made part of the Kapalbhathi technique:

STAGE-1

Find a comfortable seated position. Gently exhale all the air from lungs then inhale a little. Exhale rapidly like a gentle sneeze a sound with the mouth closed. Then inhale rapidly and begin to exhale and inhale in quick rhythm

STAGE-2

Inhale and exhale rapidly through both nostrils partially blocked. Control the air flow so that it enters through the nostrils.

STAGE-3

Inhale and exhale through the right nostril with the left nostril fully blocked. Breathe in and out of the same nostril. Switch after at least 5 breaths. So this time inhalations and exhalations are done through the left nostril.

STAGE-4

Inhale through the right nostril and exhale through the left.

STAGE-5

Inhale through both nostrils and exhale through the left then inhale through both nostrils and exhale through the right.

KAPALBHATI

FINDINGS AND RESULTS

The study was conducted to find out the effects of Kapalbhati on body fat percentage and water content. The statistical analysis of data collected on thirty (N=30) subjects. For the chosen variable, the results pertaining to significant difference, if any, between experimental and control groups were assessed by “t” test and are presented in following tables:

**TABLE-1
BODY FAT PERCENTAGE OF EXPERIMENTAL
GROUP**

	Pre-Test	Post-Test
Sample size	15	15
Arithmetic mean	22.0333	23.6800
95% CI for the mean	20.7377 to 23.3290	22.5481 to 24.8119
Variance	5.4738	4.1774
Standard deviation	2.3396	2.0439
Standard error of the mean	0.6041	0.5277

Paired samples t-test

Mean difference	1.6467
Standard deviation	1.7041
95% CI	0.7029 to 2.5904
Test statistic t	3.742
Degrees of Freedom (DF)	14
Two-tailed probability	P = 0.0022

TABLE-2
BODY FAT PERCENTAGE OF CONTROL GROUP

	Pre-Test	Post-Test
Sample size	15	15
Arithmetic mean	10.2467	10.3267
95% CI for the mean	8.8941 to 11.5992	9.0295 to 11.6238
Variance	5.9655	5.4864
Standard deviation	2.4424	2.3423
Standard error of the mean	0.6306	0.6048

Paired samples t-test

Mean difference	0.08000
Standard deviation	0.6732
95% CI	-0.2928 to 0.4528
Test statistic t	0.460
Degrees of Freedom (DF)	14
Two-tailed probability	P = 0.6524

TABLE-3
MEAN, STANDARD DEVIATION (SD), STANDARD ERROR OF MEAN (SEM) OF BODY FAT PERCENTAGE OF EXPERIMENTAL AND CONTROL GROUP

Group	Number	Mean	S.D.	SEM	't' Value
Experimental (Pre-test)	15	22.0333	2.3396	0.6041	3.742
Experimental (Post-test)	15	23.6800	2.0439	0.5277	
Control (Pre-test)	15	10.2467	2.4424	0.6306	0.460
Control (Post-test)	15	10.3267	2.3423	0.6048	

*Significant at 0.05 level of confidence.

"t" .05 (14) = 2.145

Table-3 shows that the mean of body fat percentage of pre-test of experimental group and post-test of experimental group was 22.0333 and 23.6800 respectively, whereas the mean of body fat percentage of pre-test of control and post-test of control group was 10.2467 and 10.3267. The "t" value in case of experimental group was 3.742 and for control group it was 0.460. Since cal. t (=3.742) > tab t .05 (14) (=2.145), Ho (null hypothesis) is rejected at .05 level of significance. Thus it may be concluded that twelve week training program of Kapalbhathi on university yoginis showed significant effect in body fat percentage. As per the study the above remark can be given at 95% confidence. The graphical representation of responses has been exhibited in figure-1.

FIGURE-1
P-VALUE, TWO TAILED AND ONE TAILED PROBABILITY VALUES OF A T-TEST OF EXPERIMENTAL GROUP OF BODY FAT PERCENTAGE

FIGURE-2
P-VALUE, TWO TAILED AND ONE TAILED PROBABILITY VALUES OF
A T-TEST OF CONTROL GROUP OF
BODY FAT PERCENTAGE

TABLE-4
WATER CONTENT OF EXPERIMENTAL
GROUP

	Pre-Test	Post-Test
Sample size	15	15
Arithmetic mean	53.8400	54.5933
95% CI for the mean	52.4805 to 55.1995	53.2374 to 55.9492
Variance	6.0269	5.9950
Standard deviation	2.4550	2.4485
Standard error of the mean	0.6339	0.6322

Paired samples t-test

Mean difference	0.7533
Standard deviation	0.4340
95% CI	0.5130 to 0.9937
Test statistic t	6.722
Degrees of Freedom (DF)	14
Two-tailed probability	P < 0.0001

TABLE-5
WATER CONTENT OF CONTROL
GROUP

	Pre-Test	Post-Test
Sample size	15	15
Arithmetic mean	56.3067	56.5533
95% CI for the mean	55.2592 to 57.3541	55.1276 to 57.9791
Variance	3.5778	6.6284
Standard deviation	1.8915	2.5746
Standard error of the mean	0.4884	0.6647

Paired samples t-test

Mean difference	0.2467
Standard deviation	1.9420
95% CI	-0.8288 to 1.3221
Test statistic t	0.492
Degrees of Freedom (DF)	14
Two-tailed probability	P = 0.6304

TABLE-6
MEAN, STANDARD DEVIATION (SD), STANDARD ERROR OF MEAN (SEM) OF BODY WATER CONTENT OF EXPERIMENTAL AND CONTROL GROUP

Group	Number	Mean	S.D.	SEM	't' Value
Experimental (Pre-test)	15	53.8400	2.4550	0.6339	6.722
Experimental (Post-test)	15	54.5933	2.4485	0.1330	
Control (Pre-test)	15	56.3067	1.8915	0.4884	0.492
Control (Post-test)	15	56.5533	2.5746	0.6322	

*Significant at 0.05 level of confidence.

"t" .05 (14) = 2.145

Table-3 shows that the mean of water content of pre-test of experimental group and post-test of experimental group was 53.8400 and 54.5933 respectively, whereas the mean of water content of pre-test of control and post-test of control group was 56.3067 and 56.5533. The "t" value in case of experimental group was 6.722 and for control group it was 0.492. Since cal. t (=6.722) > tab t .05 (14) (=2.145), Ho (null hypothesis) is rejected at .05 level of significance. Thus it may be concluded that twelve week training program of Kapalbhathi of University yoginis showed significant improvement in water content. As per the study the above remark can be given at 95% confidence. The graphical representation of responses has been exhibited in figure-2.

FIGURE-3
P-VALUE, TWO TAILED AND ONE TAILED PROBABILITY VALUES OF A T-TEST OF EXPERIMENTAL GROUP OF WATER CONTENT

FIGURE-4
P-VALUE, TWO TAILED AND ONE TAILED PROBABILITY VALUES OF
A T-TEST OF CONTROL GROUP OF WATER CONTENT

STATISTICAL PROCEDURE USED

The random group design was used for the study. Two groups were made of the subjects each comprising of 15 subjects. The difference in the mean of each group for selected variable was tested for the significance of difference by “t” test. The level of significance was set at 0.05.

Hypothesis:

$$H_0: \mu_y = \mu_x$$

$$H_1: \mu_y \geq \mu_x$$

Level of significance: 0.05

Inference:

Since calculated “t” is greater than tab t.05, Ho (null hypothesis) may be rejected at 0.05 level of significance. Thus it may be concluded that twelve week training program of selected Kapalbhathi on University yoginis leads to significant effect in body fat percentage and water body content. As per the study the above remark can be given at 95% confidence.

DISCUSSION

From the results it is evident that the twelve week Kapalbhathi training programme had shown a significant improvement in body fat percentage and body water content. The findings are supported by the study conducted by Udupa K.N. on “Yogic and Non Yogic exercise: Improved Physiological variables of students” to determine the effects of yogic exercise on Physiological variables showed a statistically significant ($P < .001$) improvement. [5]

CONCLUSIONS

Findings of this exploratory study suggest that the treatment of twelve week Kapalbhathi training programme showed significant effect on body fat percentage and body water content.

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SHORT PERSONAL PRESENTATION SATPAL YADAV, M.Phil (AUTHOR)

Mr. Satpal Yadav, M.Phil was born on January 25th, 1982. He received his B.P.E., M.P.E. and M.Phil degrees in Physical Education from Lakshmbai National Institute of Physical Education (Deemed University) Gwalior (M.P.) INDIA. He is pursuing his Ph.D. (Doctor of Philosophy in Physical Education) from Lakshmbai National Institute of Physical Education (Deemed University) Gwalior (M.P.) INDIA. He is the member of federation technical official of India awarded by Athletic federation of India. He joined the department of Physical Education of Lovely Professional University, Jalandhar as Lecturer of Physical Education in September; 2008. His areas of interest include Biomechanics and Kinesiology.